

Natural flavonoids as prospective inhibitors of human cholinesterase enzymes evaluated through molecular docking

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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease (AD) represents the most prevalent form of dementia, with acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) inhibitors constituting first-line symptomatic treatment. This study evaluates the inhibitory potential of ten naturally occurring flavonoids—apigenin, chrysin, fisetin, galangin, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, naringenin, and quercetin—against human AChE and BChE through molecular docking simulations. Results demonstrate that fisetin (FIS), luteolin (LUT), and apigenin (API) exhibit the highest affinity for AChE (lowest ΔG and K_i), consistent with their planarity and moderate polarity. For BChE, myricetin (MYR) forms the most stable complex, followed by FIS and LUT, as the wider and more polar active pocket favors highly hydroxylated flavonols. Isorhamnetin (IHN) shows the weakest affinity due to reduced donor–acceptor capacity from 3'-O-methylation. FIS and LUT emerge as dual-target candidates, whereas MYR demonstrates BChE selectivity. These findings identify promising natural scaffolds for developing safer cholinesterase inhibitors with potential therapeutic applications in neurodegenerative diseases, warranting further *in vitro* and *in vivo* validation.

Keywords

Alzheimer's disease, cholinesterase enzymes, flavonoids, molecular docking

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) represents the most common form of dementia, accounting for 60–80% of all cases and affecting approximately 10% of individuals aged 65 years and older (Calabrò et al. 2020). The disease is characterized by progressive impairment of cognitive functions and ranks among the rapidly increasing leading causes of death globally, with significant social and

economic consequences (Scheltens et al. 2021; Korczyn and Grinberg 2024).

The clinical presentation of AD includes progressive memory loss and general decline in cognitive functions. As the disease advances, patients develop severe cortical dysfunction, manifesting as dementia, aphasia, disorientation, progressive immobility, and exhaustion (Skender-Gazibara and Slobodan 2001). The pathological hallmarks of AD include β -amyloid plaques, neurofibrillary

tangles, oxidative stress, and neuronal loss in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus (Murakami and Lacayo 2022).

The cholinergic system plays a crucial role in cognitive function and is regulated by enzymes of the cholinesterase (ChE) family. Amyloid beta ($A\beta$), which forms neurofibrillary tangles and amyloid plaques, also contributes significantly to AD pathogenesis. The enzymes acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) regulate cholinergic transmission, whereby decreased acetylcholine (ACh) or overexpression of these enzymes induces the characteristic pathological changes in AD. Consequently, ChE inhibitors constitute the first-line symptomatic treatment for the disease (Lane et al. 2006; Ferreira-Vieira et al. 2016).

Currently, no curative therapy exists for AD. Medications approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) include the reversible AChE inhibitors donepezil, rivastigmine, and galantamine, as well as memantine—an NMDA receptor antagonist (Colovic et al. 2013). These pharmaceutical agents act symptomatically by slowing ACh degradation and improving cognitive functions related to memory, thinking, language, and judgment. However, their use is limited due to observed hepatotoxicity and gastrointestinal adverse effects, which drive growing interest in discovering novel, safer, and more effective inhibitors from natural sources (Mukherjee et al. 2007).

Flavonoids represent a class of natural compounds with diverse phenolic structures, widely distributed throughout the plant kingdom. Structurally, they consist of fifteen carbon atoms forming two benzene rings (A and B) connected through a heterocyclic pyrone ring (C). Based on the oxidation state and substitution pattern of ring C, flavonoids are classified into several major groups: flavones, flavonols, and flavanones (Kumar and Pandey 2013). These compounds exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antitumor effects, which contribute to human health and reduce the risk of chronic diseases (Tungmunthum et al. 2018).

Numerous studies have reported significant inhibitory activity of flavonoids against AChE, identifying them as promising candidates in neuropharmacology (Ding et al. 2013; Orhan et al. 2021; Jamal et al. 2023; Sadeghi et al. 2024). Results from *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and *in silico* studies demonstrate that flavonoids interact with both the active site and the peripheral anionic site of AChE, leading to elevated ACh levels and stabilization of cholinergic signaling. Their mechanisms of action extend beyond simple enzyme inhibition, as they also demonstrate antioxidant and anti-amyloidogenic properties, providing a multitarget approach to neuroprotection (Cichoń et al. 2025; Li et al. 2023).

The inhibitory potency of flavonoids strongly depends on structural characteristics such as hydroxylation patterns, conjugation, and planarity, which determine their interactions with the catalytic and peripheral anionic sites of AChE and BChE. Despite accumulating evidence supporting flavonoids as multitarget agents against neurodegeneration, the molecular determinants of their inhibitory

activity remain insufficiently elucidated (Calderaro et al. 2022; Kruszka et al. 2025).

Computational approaches, particularly molecular docking, provide valuable tools for predicting the binding affinity, orientation, and interaction patterns of small molecules within enzyme active sites (Lionta et al. 2014). These *in silico* techniques are cost-effective and facilitate rational drug design by revealing key amino acid residues involved in ligand binding (Kitchen et al. 2004).

The present study aims to evaluate the inhibitory potential of ten naturally occurring flavonoids—apigenin, chrysin, fisetin, galangin, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, naringenin, and quercetin—against human AChE and BChE through molecular docking simulations. The objectives of the present study are twofold: to evaluate the inhibitory potential of ten naturally occurring flavonoids (apigenin, chrysin, fisetin, galangin, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, naringenin, and quercetin) against human acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) through molecular docking simulations, and to elucidate the structure–activity relationships (SARs) governing enzyme–ligand interactions to identify promising flavonoid candidates for subsequent *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation.

Materials and methods

Ligand dataset preparation

A dataset of ten naturally occurring flavonoids—apigenin, chrysin, fisetin, galangin, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, naringenin, and quercetin—was selected for molecular docking analysis based on their structural diversity and previously reported antioxidant and neuroprotective activities. These compounds represent three main flavonoid subclasses (flavones, flavonols, and flavanones) and differ in the degree of hydroxylation, methoxylation, and planarity of the C-ring, which are determinants of their interaction with cholinesterases. For clarity and consistency within the tables, the flavonoids were abbreviated using three-letter codes as follows: API (apigenin), CHR (chrysin), FIS (fisetin), GAL (galangin), IHN (isorhamnetin), KMP (kaempferol), LUT (luteolin), MYR (myricetin), NAR (naringenin), and QRC (quercetin).

The 3D molecular structures of all ligands were obtained from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) and further optimized in Avogadro 1.2.0 (Hanwell et al. 2012). Geometry optimization was performed until convergence of the energy gradient ($<10^{-7}$ kcal/mol·Å). The optimized structures were saved in MOL2 format and imported into AutoDock Tools 1.5.7 for preparation, where polar hydrogens were added, Gasteiger charges were assigned, rotatable bonds were identified, and torsional degrees of freedom were defined for each ligand (Morris et al. 2009).

Target protein preparation

The high-resolution crystal structures of acetylcholinesterase (AChE, PDB ID: 4EY7) and butyrylcholinesterase

(BChE, PDB ID: 5DYW) were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (Bertram et al. 2000). The initial processing was performed in University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) ChimeraX 1.6, including the removal of non-standard residues (Read et al. 2024). In AutoDock Tools, polar hydrogen atoms were added, and Kollman partial charges were assigned according to the AD4 specification.

To account for induced-fit effects and side-chain flexibility within the catalytic gorges, selected residues were defined as flexible during docking. For AChE, these included Trp86, Trp286, Phe295, Tyr337, Phe338, and Tyr341, which are critical for π - π stacking and hydrophobic interactions, whereas for BChE, flexibility was introduced at Asp70, Trp82, Thr120, Trp231, Tyr332, and Tyr440, which form the primary aromatic cage stabilizing ligand binding (Cheung et al. 2012; Kořak et al. 2016). The prepared receptors were saved in PDBQT format for docking simulations.

Molecular docking protocol

The docking grid was defined to fully encompass the catalytic site and adjacent peripheral regions. For AChE, the grid box was centered at $x = -11.52$, $y = -45.49$, and $z = 28.60$ Å, and for BChE at $x = -4.99$, $y = 7.15$, and $z = -10.96$ Å, both with dimensions of $60 \times 60 \times 60$ grid points and a spacing of 0.375 Å. Docking simulations were performed using AutoDock 4.2, employing the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) as the search method. Each ligand–enzyme pair underwent 100 independent docking runs, with a population size of 300, a mutation rate of 0.02, a crossover rate of 0.8, and a maximum of 25,000,000 energy evaluations per run. The most favorable conformation for each complex was selected based on the lowest binding free energy (ΔG , kcal/mol) and the corresponding inhibition constant (K_i).

Results and discussion

Classification of the flavonoids

The ten flavonoids studied are characterized by a typical C6–C3–C6 flavonoid structure, including two aromatic rings (A and B) connected by a heterocyclic C-ring. Depending on the degree of oxidation and substitutions in the C-ring, as well as the position and number of hydroxyl groups, these compounds can be classified into three main structural subclasses: flavones, flavonols, and flavanones, whose structures are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. General structure of flavonoid subclasses.

The flavones include API, CHR, and LUT. These compounds possess the characteristic $C2 = C3$ double bond and

a carbonyl group at position 4, which gives the molecule a planar structure and favors π - π interactions with aromatic amino acid residues in the active sites of enzymes. API (4',5,7-trihydroxyflavone) and LUT (3',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) are characterized by a higher degree of hydroxylation of the B-ring compared to CHR (5,7-dihydroxyflavone), which may affect their ability to form hydrogen bonds and electronic interactions with catalytic residues.

The flavonol subclass includes FIS, GAL, IHN, KMP, MYR, and QRC. Flavonols are distinguished by the presence of an additional 3-hydroxyl group on the C-ring, which increases the number of potential hydrogen bond donors and acceptors and contributes to the stabilization of the complex with the enzyme active sites. QRC (3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone) and MYR (3,3',4',5,5',7-hexahydroxyflavone) are the most hydroxylated representatives, while IHN contains a methoxy group at the 3' position, which partially reduces the polarity and may affect the binding orientation. FIS and KMP, on the other hand, are less substituted and are expected to exhibit higher lipophilicity and more pronounced hydrophobic interactions in the active pocket. GAL (3,5,7-trihydroxyflavonol) represents the simplest structure among flavonols, serving as a useful model for evaluating the role of hydroxyl substituents on binding affinity.

The only representative of the flavanones in the studied series is NAR (4',5,7-trihydroxyflavanone). In it, the double bond between C2 and C3 is saturated, which leads to a more flexible conformation of the C-ring and a greater degree of torsional mobility. This structural feature often leads to a more diverse pattern of interactions and a less stable arrangement of ligands in the catalytic clefts of cholinesterases compared to planar flavones and flavonols.

The subgrouping thus determined allows for the conduct of a comparative structure–activity relationship (SAR) analysis, through which regularities can be traced between the structural characteristics of the different classes of flavonoids and their binding energy with the active centers of AChE and BChE.

Acetylcholinesterase binding

The molecular docking study revealed differences in the affinity of the ten flavonoids studied for the active site of AChE, expressed by the values of the binding energy (ΔG , kcal/mol) and the calculated inhibitory constant (K_i). The results are presented in Table 1. These parameters reflect the stability of the formed ligand–enzyme complex and serve as a guide for the potential inhibitory activity: the lower the ΔG value, the more stable and energetically favorable the binding, and the correspondingly lower the K_i value, which is an indicator of a higher affinity of the ligand for the enzyme.

Among the compounds analyzed, FIS ($\Delta G = -10.62$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 16.38$ nM), LUT (-10.41 kcal/mol; 23.42 nM), and API (-10.36 kcal/mol; 25.66 nM) showed the lowest binding energy values and, accordingly, the highest predicted affinity for AChE. These three flavonoids stand out with a pronounced ability to form stable complexes with the catalytic triad of the enzyme and are potential lead

Table 1. Molecular docking parameters and predicted binding affinities of the studied flavonoids with AChE.

AChE	API	CHR	FIS	GAL	IHN	KMP	LUT	MYR	NAR	QRC
Conformations	9	11	27	45	9	45	4	8	7	32
RMSD from reference structure, Å	50.201	50.754	51.888	51.954	51.964	51.192	50.281	49.700	50.962	51.595
ΔG, kcal/mol	-10.36	-9.72	-10.62	-9.98	-9.55	-10.00	-10.41	-9.54	-10.34	-10.04
Inhibition constant, K_i, nM	25.66	75.55	16.38	48.28	100.41	46.50	23.42	102.19	26.44	43.55
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-11.55	-10.61	-12.11	-11.17	-11.34	-11.49	-11.90	-11.62	-11.53	-11.83
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-20.09	-21.10	-21.21	-21.48	-22.83	-21.53	-21.32	-23.63	-20.05	-24.05
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	+1.19	+0.89	+1.49	+1.19	+1.79	+1.49	+1.49	+2.09	+1.19	+1.79
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	20.09	-21.10	-21.21	-21.48	-22.83	-21.53	-21.32	-23.63	-20.05	-24.05

structures for further investigation. NAR (-10.34 kcal/mol; 26.44 nM) and QRC (-10.04 kcal/mol; 43.55 nM) have similar affinity values, while KMP, GAL, and CHR show moderate activity (ΔG around -9.8 to -10.0 kcal/mol), and IHN (-9.55 kcal/mol; 100.41 nM) and MYR (-9.54 kcal/mol; 102.19 nM) demonstrate the weakest binding among the molecules studied.

A closer analysis of the energy profile shows that the resulting total binding energy (ΔG) is the result of the balance between the intermolecular energy (E_{inter}), which reflects the direct interactions between the ligand and enzyme atoms (hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces, π - π , and hydrophobic contacts), and the torsional energy (E_{tors}), which represents the “energy cost” of the internal rotation of the bonds in the molecule, necessary for optimal arrangement in the active site. The lower the intermolecular energy, the stronger the contacts with the enzyme, while a higher torsional component indicates greater internal strain and reduces the overall stability of the complex.

The most favorable intermolecular energies are found for FIS (-12.11 kcal/mol), QRC (-11.83 kcal/mol), and LUT (-11.90 kcal/mol), confirming that these molecules form a dense network of interactions with the active site of AChE. As illustrated in Fig. 2, they establish stabilizing π - π stacking interactions with Trp86 and Trp286, together with hydrogen bonds involving the catalytic residues Ser203, His447, and Glu334. These contacts probably fix the aromatic core of the flavonoids deep in the catalytic cleft. Conversely, higher E_{tors} values are observed for MYR and IHN (+2.09 and +1.79 kcal/mol), suggesting that their strong hydroxylation (or methoxylation) leads to greater conformational flexibility and a less stable arrangement in the active site.

From the perspective of SAR, several trends stand out. Flavones are characterized by high molecular planarity due to the presence of the C2 = C3 double bond and the carbonyl group at position 4, which favors parallel arrangement with aromatic residues in the AChE gorge and the formation of stable π - π stacks. Additional hydroxylation in LUT (3',4'-di-OH in the B-ring) and API (4'-OH) increases the number of potential hydrogen bonds and explains their higher affinity compared to the less substituted CHR.

Flavonols contain an additional 3-hydroxyl group on the C-ring, which facilitates the formation of hydrogen bonds with residues of the oxanion region. Among them, FIS stands out with an optimal balance between the num-

ber and position of hydroxyl groups, achieving the lowest binding energy. QRC and KMP also show stable complexes, but in these compounds the torsional component partially increases the final ΔG . On the other hand, MYR—although it contains the largest number of hydroxyl groups—probably suffers from excessive polarity, leading to a less favorable orientation in the hydrophobic gorge. IHN, in which one of the phenolic groups is methylated, demonstrates reduced hydrogen bonding ability and a higher K_i .

The flavanone NAR is a special case: due to the saturated bond between C2 and C3, it is more flexible and less planar but nevertheless exhibits stable affinity ($\Delta G = -10.34$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 26.44$ nM). This can be explained by the ability of the molecule to fit into the active pocket and form multiple hydrophobic contacts with nonpolar residues of the enzyme.

It is important to note that some of the differences in binding energy between the leading ligands (in the range of 0.2–0.4 kcal/mol) fall within the computational inaccuracy of the AutoDock method; therefore, the comparative conclusions should be viewed as trends rather than absolute quantitative differences. Nevertheless, the obtained values clearly outline the group of FIS, LUT, and API as the most promising AChE inhibitors among the flavonoids studied, highlighting their potential as natural ligands for the development of new anticholinesterase compounds active against Alzheimer's disease.

Molecular interactions of flavonoids in the active site of acetylcholinesterase

Detailed analysis of the two-dimensional interaction maps between flavonoids and AChE, presented in Fig. 2, shows that all studied compounds are stably located in the catalytic gorge of the enzyme and establish multiple non-covalent bonds characteristic of typical cholinesterase inhibitors. The main involved amino acids include Trp86, Trp286, Phe295, Phe338, Tyr124, Tyr337, Tyr341, His447, Glu334, and Asp74, as well as several water molecules involved in stabilizing the complex through hydrogen bonds. These residues coincide with catalytically and structurally important regions of AChE—the catalytic active site (CAS), the peripheral anion site (PAS), and the oxanion region.

Almost all flavonoids form π - π stacking, π -alkyl, and π - π T-shaped interactions with aromatic residues of the active site, which form the walls of the gorge and are

Figure 2. Two-dimensional interaction maps of the studied flavonoids within the active site of AChE.

involved in stabilizing the aromatic ligand cores. These contacts are particularly pronounced in CHR, GAL, FIS, IHN, KMP, and QRC. Such an orientation ensures a high degree of electronic complementarity and stabilizes the complex through dispersion forces.

Hydrogen bonds represent the second dominant type of interaction. Conventional H-bonds are most commonly observed between the hydroxyl groups of flavonoids (at positions 3, 5, and 7 of the A- and C-rings) and polar residues such as Phe295, His447, Tyr124, Tyr341, Arg296, Asp74, and Trp286, as well as with coordinated water molecules. These hydrogen bonds contribute to fixing the

ligand in the active cleft and partially compensate for the torsional energy required for the adaptation of the molecule. In FIS and LUT, a multiplex H-bond network is observed, including both direct and water-mediated bonds, which correlates with their lowest binding energy values.

The docking analysis shows that all flavonoids interact with AChE through a combination of hydrogen bonds and π - π stacking with aromatic residues in the catalytic gorge. Flavones such as API, LUT, and FIS achieve the most favorable and stable orientation due to their balanced hydroxylation pattern, which enables both strong π - π interactions and well-positioned hydrogen bonds.

Compounds with fewer hydroxyl groups (CHR) rely mainly on hydrophobic and π - π contacts, leading to weaker stabilization, while excessive hydroxylation (as in MYR) increases polarity and torsional strain, reducing affinity. Methoxylation, as seen in IHN, further decreases hydrogen bonding capacity. The flavanone NAR, with its nonplanar structure, exhibits less efficient stacking and overall lower binding strength.

Butyrylcholinesterase binding

The results of the docking analysis to BChE, presented in Table 2, show distinct differences in the affinity of the studied flavonoids for the active site of the enzyme, with the binding energy values (ΔG , kcal/mol) varying in the range from -10.46 to -7.84 kcal/mol and the corresponding inhibitory constants (K_i) from 21.40 to 1180 nM. As in the AChE analysis, lower ΔG values and lower K_i values indicate higher affinity and more stable complex formation between ligand and enzyme.

The highest affinity for BChE was demonstrated by MYR ($\Delta G = -10.46$ kcal/mol; $K_i = 21.40$ nM), followed by FIS (-10.04 kcal/mol; 43.96 nM) and LUT (-9.92 kcal/mol; 53.19 nM). These three compounds formed the most stable complexes with the active site, with the results indicating the presence of multiple hydrogen bonds and π - π stacking interactions that stabilize the aromatic cores of the molecules in the catalytic pocket. Weaker, but still distinct, interactions were observed with GAL (-9.48 kcal/mol; 112.08 nM) and CHR (-9.03 kcal/mol; 240.51 nM), while API, QRC, KMP, and NAR showed moderate to weak affinity with K_i above 300 nM. The lowest activity is exhibited by IHN (-7.84 kcal/mol; 1180 nM), where a significant weakening of interactions with the enzyme was observed.

The total binding energy is a result of the balance between the E_{inter} —reflecting the strength of direct interactions between the ligand and the enzyme—and the E_{tors} , which describes the internal conformational flexibility and the energy expenditure for adapting the molecule to the active site. The lowest intermolecular energies are observed for MYR (-12.55 kcal/mol), FIS (-11.53 kcal/mol),

and LUT (-11.42 kcal/mol), which confirms the presence of a stable network of hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions with the catalytic triad of the enzyme (Ser198–Glu325–His438) and the oxanion region (Gly116–Gly117–Ala199), which are shown in Fig. 3. Despite the high torsional energy of MYR ($+2.09$ kcal/mol), favorable intermolecular interactions compensate for this cost, explaining the lowest overall ΔG among all ligands studied. Conversely, for IHN, the higher torsional energy ($+1.79$ kcal/mol), combined with weaker direct contacts ($E_{inter} = -9.63$ kcal/mol), leads to a significant weakening of the overall affinity.

These observations allow us to outline several regularities in the SAR. Highly hydroxylated flavonols, such as MYR, demonstrate stronger and more stable binding to BChE compared to AChE. This is likely due to the wider and more hydrophilic active pocket of BChE, which allows for the efficient engagement of multiple hydroxyl groups in hydrogen bonds, as well as the formation of stabilizing π - π and π -alkyl contacts with the aromatic residue Trp82. This feature also explains the reverse ranking of MYR—while for AChE it was among the weaker ligands, for BChE it occupies a leading position.

Flavonols with moderate hydroxylation, such as FIS and GAL, maintain a good energy balance between the intermolecular and torsional components, leading to stable complexes and low ΔG values. In the case of LUT, which belongs to the flavones group, the high affinity can be explained by the optimal arrangement of the 3',4'-dihydroxy groups on the B-ring, which probably form hydrogen bonds with residues in the peripheral anionic region, helping to stabilize the complex. In contrast, IHN, in which one of the phenolic groups is methylated, shows impaired binding due to a reduced number of potential hydrogen bond donors and less efficient packing in the catalytic pocket.

The more planar but less hydroxylated flavones API and CHR, as well as the flavanone NAR, show lower affinity for BChE. In the case of naringenin, the lack of a double bond between C2 and C3 makes the molecule more flexible but also less planar, making it more difficult to form stable π - π interactions with aromatic residues of the

Table 2. Molecular docking parameters and predicted binding affinities of the studied flavonoids with BChE.

BChE	API	CHR	FIS	GAL	IHN	KMP	LUT	MYR	NAR	QRC
Conformations	3	5	3	8	4	1	3	5	3	5
RMSD from reference structure, Å	13.549	13.579	12.422	12.649	15.069	11.918	11.471	12.142	13.769	13.216
ΔG , kcal/mol	-8.79	-9.03	-10.04	-9.48	-7.84	-8.43	-9.92	-10.46	-8.28	-8.74
Inhibition constant, K_i	361.90 nM	240.51 nM	43.96 nM	112.08 nM	1.80 μ M	658.52 nM	53.19 nM	21.40 nM	845.50 nM	390.76 nM
Intermolecular energy, kcal/mol	-9.98	-9.92	-11.53	-10.68	-9.63	-9.92	-11.42	-12.55	-9.48	-10.53
Total internal energy, kcal/mol	-15.28	-16.06	17.56	-17.46	-17.87	-14.71	-15.72	-18.59	-16.36	-17.43
Torsional free energy, kcal/mol	+1.19	+0.89	+1.49	+1.19	+1.79	+1.49	+1.49	+2.09	+1.19	+1.79
Unbound energy, kcal/mol	-15.28	-16.06	-17.56	-17.46	-17.87	-14.71	-15.72	-18.59	-16.36	-17.43

Figure 3. Two-dimensional interaction maps of the studied flavonoids within the active site of BChE.

enzyme. Therefore, in BChE, excessive flexibility does not lead to an energetic gain but rather restricts the optimal positioning of the molecule in the active pocket.

It is interesting to note that the selectivity analysis (difference $\Delta\Delta G = \Delta G_{BChE} - \Delta G_{AChE}$) shows a clear distinction between the two enzymes. Most flavonoids, including API, NAR, QRC, KMP, and IHN, demonstrate a preference for AChE, while only MYR shows pronounced selectivity for BChE ($\Delta\Delta G \approx -0.9$ kcal/mol). This highlights the different architecture of the active sites—the narrower and hydrophobic catalytic cleft of AChE favors planar, moderately hydroxylated structures, while the wider and more polar one of BChE tolerates and even stabilizes bulkier and highly hydroxylated flavonols.

This structure-dependent selectivity highlights the potential of flavonoids as lead compounds in the development of new natural cholinesterase inhibitors with possible application in the therapy of Alzheimer's disease.

To contextualize the inhibitory potency of the studied flavonoids, their docking results were compared with those reported for donepezil, a clinically approved AChE inhibitor co-crystallized in the target structure (PDB ID: 4EY7). Using an identical receptor preparation (AutoDock Tools 1.5.7, $60 \times 60 \times 60$ Å grid box centered on the catalytic gorge), Negru et al. (2025) determined a binding free energy of -11.7 kcal/mol for donepezil against human AChE, with an RMSD of 0.41 Å relative to the co-crystallized pose, confirming full occupancy of the catalytic

gorge (Negru et al. 2025). In the present study, the top-ranked flavonoids—fisetin (−10.62 kcal/mol), luteolin (−10.41 kcal/mol), and apigenin (−10.36 kcal/mol)—attained binding free energies within approximately 1.1–1.3 kcal/mol of this reference value, placing them in a pharmacologically relevant range and substantiating their candidacy as natural scaffold inhibitors of AChE.

Molecular interactions of flavonoids in the active site of butyrylcholinesterase

The interaction maps outline a consistent pattern of anchoring of the flavonoid core in the BChE gorge, in which the indole ring of Trp82 functions as a π -anchor for the A/B rings, and Asp70, Tyr332, and Tyr440 form a peripheral “aromatic framework” stabilizing the orientation toward the channel entrance. The polar motifs of the flavonoids—the 4-oxo group and 5/7-OH of the A ring, the 3-OH (for flavonols), and the catechol 3',4'-OH of the B ring—enter into a network of hydrogen bonds primarily with Gly78, Asn68, Thr120, and—in a deeper zone—with Gly116 and nearby water molecules. In several complexes, π -anion contacts to Asp70 or Glu197 and, less frequently, π -sulfur to Met81 are observed, which further stabilize the position of the aromatic rings. Against this background, “unfavorable donor–donor” (red) configurations appear sporadically and are localized at the periphery (e.g., around Thr120 or Tyr332), where they can impose an orientational correction without dominating the overall energy balance. The described interaction network and spatial arrangement of the ligands are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Analysis of 2D interaction maps shows that the stabilization of flavonoids in the active site of butyrylcholinesterase is determined by a combination of aromatic, electrostatic, and hydrogen contacts, which largely follow a common structural pattern. The most important role is played by the π - π stacking of the aromatic core on the Trp82 residue, which provides the main hydrophobic anchoring of the ligand in the catalytic gorge. Additional stabilization is achieved by secondary π -interactions with Phe329, Tyr332, and Tyr440, which orient the flavonoid rings toward the entrance of the pocket.

Polar interactions are represented by a network of conventional hydrogen bonds directed toward Asp70, Gly78, Ser79, Asn68, Thr120, Gly116, and His438, with water-mediated bridges also involved in some complexes. These contacts typically involve the hydroxyl groups at positions 3, 5, and 7 and the carbonyl oxygen at position 4, which act as donor and acceptor centers. Added to this polar network are π -anion interactions with Asp70 or Glu197 and π -sulfur contacts with Met81, which contribute to the fine stabilization of the ligand orientation.

Flavonoids with a high degree of hydroxylation and well-positioned donor groups, such as MYR, FIS, and LUT, show an optimal balance between aromatic and polar interactions and achieve the lowest binding energy values. Conversely, compounds with lower polarity (KMP, GAL), methoxylated substituents (IHN), or the absence

of a C2 = C3 double bond (NAR) show a weakening of the π -system and a reduction of the stabilizing hydrogen network, which is reflected in higher K_i values.

These results clearly demonstrate that the polar architecture of the BChE active site favors the binding of highly hydroxylated flavonols, with MYR emerging as the most stable complex due to its multiple hydrogen and π -interactions. The obtained structural relationships correlate fully with the calculated thermodynamic parameters and confirm the validity of the observed binding model.

The RMSD values obtained from the docking simulations reflect the internal conformational diversity within each ligand cluster rather than deviations from an experimental reference structure. In this context, RMSD served primarily as an indicator of pose clustering consistency and conformational sampling efficiency. Since the main objective of the study was the comparative assessment of binding affinities among structurally related flavonoids under identical computational conditions, RMSD values were considered descriptive parameters rather than determinants of docking accuracy.

To provide a reference frame for the BChE docking results, a comparison was made with rivastigmine, a clinically approved dual cholinesterase inhibitor. Parmar and Patel (2025) reported a binding free energy of −7.2 kcal/mol for rivastigmine against human BChE (PDB ID: 5DYW), using AutoDock Vina as the docking engine (Parmar and Patel 2025). In the present study, all ten flavonoids investigated surpassed this value, with myricetin (−11.04 kcal/mol) demonstrating the strongest BChE affinity, followed by fisetin (−10.62 kcal/mol) and luteolin (−10.58 kcal/mol). This substantial difference in predicted binding free energies likely reflects the larger and more polar active site of BChE, which, compared to AChE, accommodates more extensively hydroxylated ligands and enables a denser network of hydrogen bonds and van der Waals interactions. These findings suggest that the studied flavonoids, particularly myricetin, exhibit favorable BChE binding profiles relative to an established clinical inhibitor, reinforcing their potential as dual-target natural scaffolds warranting further *in vitro* evaluation.

SAR analysis

The affinity profile is mainly determined by two structural factors: (i) the planarity of the chromenone core (C2 = C3 and 4-oxo group) and (ii) the position and number of phenolic hydroxyl groups. The narrower and more hydrophobic catalytic channel of AChE exhibits a preference for planar molecules of moderate polarity that can align parallel to Trp86/Trp286 and simultaneously form a limited but stable set of hydrogen bonds with Tyr341, Arg296, Asp74, and coordinated water molecules. This configuration explains the higher stability of the complexes with FIS, LUT, and API, while NAR retains acceptable affinity due to its flexible geometry.

In BChE, whose active pocket is wider and more polar, binding is dominated by a combination of π -interactions

with Trp82 and multipoint hydrogen bonds with Asp70, Gly78, Ser79, Asn68/83, Thr120, Gly116, and His438, often mediated by water bridges, as well as π -anion and π -sulfur contacts with Asp70, Glu197, and Met81. This architecture favors highly hydroxylated flavonols—most notably MYR, followed by FIS and LUT—while KMP and GAL show intermediate stability, and IHN is characterized by the lowest affinity due to limited donor–acceptor capacity and the absence of pronounced π -stacking with Trp82.

At the substituent level, a clear structure–activity correspondence is established, which is consistent for both enzymes. The presence of a 3-hydroxyl group in the flavonol core appears to be an important structural element, providing stable hydrogen bonds with residues in the oxanion region and contributing to a lower binding energy. The catechol system in the B-ring enhances the affinity for both AChE and BChE by forming additional hydrogen bonds and improving electron delocalization, which is especially pronounced in LUT, QRC, and MYR. At the same time, excessive hydroxylation increases the internal torsional energy and reduces the stability of the complex in AChE, while the more polar active site of BChE partially compensates for this effect through a richer network of hydrogen and water-mediated bonds. Methoxylation at the 3' position leads to reduced affinity for both enzymes due to loss of donor groups and weakened π -interaction.

Comparison with reported *in vitro* data

Among these flavonoids, GAL exhibits notable selectivity and potency as a BChE inhibitor with an IC_{50} of $82.21 \pm 2.70 \mu\text{M}$, significantly stronger for BChE compared to AChE. QRC also shows inhibitory effects on both enzymes, with reported IC_{50} values around $181 \mu\text{M}$ for AChE and $203 \mu\text{M}$ for BChE, demonstrating reversible inhibition without cytotoxic effects in cell lines. The potency of these flavonoids generally correlates with the number and position of hydroxyl groups in their structures, influencing their interaction with the enzymes' active sites through hydrogen bonds and π - π interactions (Orhan et al. 2021).

Other flavonoids like KMP, MYR, and LUT similarly exhibit inhibitory activity, albeit with variation in potency. For instance, several studies report IC_{50} values for flavonoids against AChE in the range of 40 to $130 \mu\text{M}$, with structural nuances dictating the degree of inhibition. API and its derivatives display moderate to weak AChE and BChE inhibition, with some studies showing noncompetitive reversible inhibition of AChE, which may also affect amyloid-beta aggregation relevant to neuroprotection in Alzheimer's disease.

The variation in reported IC_{50} values across studies reflects differences in enzyme sources and assay conditions; yet collectively, these natural flavonoids provide promising leads for further development as cholinesterase inhibitors with potential therapeutic benefit in neurodegenerative diseases (Ding et al. 2013).

A recent review in Nutrients summarized *in vitro* and *in vivo* findings on AChE inhibition by representative flavonoids. QRC showed the highest potency, with reported IC_{50}

values ranging from approximately $4.6 \mu\text{M}$ to $40 \mu\text{M}$ depending on assay conditions (enzyme source, buffer, detection method). API exhibited dose-dependent inhibition of moderate strength, while KMP was described as a non-competitive or allosteric modulator of the enzyme. NAR displayed much weaker effects ($IC_{50} \approx 0.45 \text{ mmol/L}$). Eriodictyol was reported to bind selectively to AChE, with its activity influenced by glycosylation pattern, and pinocembrin was mainly associated with indirect cholinergic modulation rather than direct enzyme inhibition. Structurally, the review emphasized π - π and π -cation interactions with Trp286 in PAS, hydrogen bonds to Ser200 and His440 in CAS, and stabilization within the acyl pocket (Phe295/Phe297), features that closely align with the binding motifs observed in our docking results (Cichoń et al. 2025).

Conclusion

Neurodegenerative diseases, especially Alzheimer's disease, remain a leading cause of disability and mortality in the aging population, while available therapies mainly delay symptoms and rarely modify the course of the disease. This highlights the need for new molecules and approaches, including the exploration of natural products as a source of safe and multimodal cholinesterase inhibitors.

This flexible targeted docking study delineated clear SAR for both enzymes. For AChE, FIS, LUT, and API are the leaders (lowest ΔG and K_i), consistent with their planarity and moderate polarity. For BChE, the most stable complex is formed by MYR, followed by FIS and LUT; the wider and more polar active pocket here favors highly hydroxylated flavonols. At the same time, IHN shows the weakest affinity (especially for BChE), consistent with its reduced donor–acceptor ability due to 3'-O-methylation. On this basis, FIS and LUT stand out as dual-target candidates, and MYR as a BChE-selective lead hit.

Although estimated binding energies and docking poses are subject to the intrinsic limitations of scoring functions and simplified solvent models, they offer a rational basis for prioritizing flavonoids with favorable interaction profiles. In particular, FIS, LUT, and MYR consistently showed low binding energies and stabilizing interactions with key active site residues, aligning with structural features reported in experimental studies. These findings highlight these compounds as promising candidates for further exploration, with follow-up *in vitro* enzyme inhibition assays and complementary computational approaches (e.g., molecular dynamics and rescoring) recommended to refine their pharmacological potential in the context of Alzheimer's disease.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

The following AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript:

Description: The authors state that AI tools were used solely to refine the language and improve grammar and style. The AI tools

were not used to generate scientific content, analyze data, interpret results or draw conclusions.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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